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PREREQUISITES FOR THE EMERGENCE OF BOOK PRINTING IN UKRAINIAN LAND IN THE 16TH CENTURY AND ITS ROLE IN THE HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF CULTURE AND EDUCATION

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A historiographical review of scientific research on the Ukrainian old printed book in the 90s of the 20th – early 21st centuries is proposed. The most significant works on the topic are taken into account. The most relevant scientific research topics are established: the old printed book in the historical and cultural process of Ukraine in the 16th century; the Ukrainian old printed book by types and genres; the Ukrainian old printed book in the library collections; the art of the Ukrainian old printed book.

Key words: history of Ukrainian culture, Ukrainian old printed book, Ukrainian book publishing, history of the book business.

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БУДИНКИ І МЕМОРІАЛЬНІ МУЗЕЇ ВИДАТНИХ ПРЕДСТАВНИКІВ МУЗИЧНОГО МИСТЕЦТВА

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Беручи до уваги тенденцію останніх десятиліть, можна зазначити, що музеї можна назвати місцями зберігання не лише матеріальної, а й нематеріальної культурної спадщини. Зокрема, це можна віднести до музеїв літературного, театального та музичного профілю, оскільки поряд із матеріальними свідками перелічених музеїв досліджується, пропагується та демонструється їх роль у розвитку суспільства. Вважаємо за доцільне представити деякі музичні музеї, присвячені життю та творчості багатьох видатних діячів у галузі музики. Звичайно, неможливо обговорити тисячі таких музеїв, але необхідно надати інформацію про кілька цікавих музеїв, які стосуються кожної групи.

Ключові слова: музика, музей, меморіал, опера, диригент, експозиція

Countless museums have been established around the world dedicated to the lives and works of prominent figures in any field of music. There are house and memorial museums, museum-mansions of almost all great composers, wonderful performers. In May 2006, a ceremony was held for the unveiling of a bust of the great Azerbaijani composer Uzeyir Hajibeyli in Vienna, the capital of Austria. Five years later, in October 2011, a monument to Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart was erected in Baku, and the opening ceremony was attended by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, and the President of the Republic of Austria, Heinz Fischer.

It should be noted that the director of the Azerbaijan National Museum of art, artist, honored art worker Chingiz Farzaliyev and people's artist Natig Aliyev, who participated in the preparation of the monument to Mozart, were awarded the orders of the Republic of Austria at the Austrian Embassy in Azerbaijan in July 2015 for their project. Chingiz Farzaliyev was awarded Austria «Grand Honorary Order» by Ambassador Axel Wex, while Natig Aliyev received the «Golden Honorary Order» [1; 8].

In Vienna, the Mozart House Museum is located in the four-room apartment where the great composer lived as a tenant from 1784 to 1787. Many of Mozarts's friends used to visit this house, where the composer created numerous musical works. The museum was opened in 2006, on the eve of Mozarts;s 250 th anniversary. Currently, the museum covers not only the memorial apartment, but also the other 5 floors of the building. The exposition, built in the new halls, tells about the era of Mozart, the traditions and fashionable life of the capital of the Austrian Empire, as well as about Mozarts friends.

The museum is equipped with furniture sets typical of the end of the 18 th century. There are almost no personal belongings of Mozart in the museum. However, numerous documents and photographs, as well as original scores written by the composer himself, are displayed in the stands and showcases. And in the living room there is a clock by

the composer himself, are displayed in the stands and showcases. And in the living room there is a clock that plays the melody *Andante KV 616*, made in 1790 [2].

The house museum dedicated to the great composer also operates in the city of *Salzburg*, where he was born. Mozarts family lived in this house in 1773-1776. Here, the composer wrote symphonies, masses, serenades, concertos for piano and violin, works related to church music, and a concerto for bassoon.

In 1944, during World War II, the house where Mozart lived was destroyed, only the dance room of the house remained intact. Around this room, the great composer's house has been rebuilt and turned into a museum. The museum has an interesting collection dedicated to Mozart's life and work, as well as the development of music in Salzburg. The exposition exhibits musical instruments and interiors of that period, including personal belongings of Mozart and his family members [3].

There is also a museum dedicated to Mozart in *Prague*, the capital of the Czech Republic. Mozart first arrived in Prague in January 1787, staying at the Bertramka villa, where he worked on the opera «*Don Giovanni*». In 1791, the composer visited Prague for the last time to see the opera «*Don Giovanni*» at the Nostitz theatre, and he passed away in December of that year. Later, Mozart's children also came to the Bertramka villa, and even the composers eldest son became friends with Adolf, the son of the owner of the villa. After his father died, Adolf immortalized Mozarts memory here: in the garden, a bust of the great composer has been placed, and no one has lived in the rooms where Mozart once resided since then. Adolf fulfilled the wish of his late father and collected things related to the composers work.

In 1929, the Bertramka villa was bought by the «Mozart society». And in 1956, the composers's house-museum was opened here. Posters, manuscripts, letters, documents and engravings were placed on the walls of the seven halls of the exposition. Among the museum's unique exhibits are 13 strands of Mozarts hair, the composers's personal belongings, and the musical instruments he played. In one of the halls, the interior of the 18 th century comes to life, and all the furniture and items in this room seem to «resonate» with music.

Muzey yalnız Motsart haqqında deyil, həmçinin villanın sahibləri Dušek ailəsindən və ümumilikdə çex musiqisinin inkişafından bəhs edir. Məsələ burasındadır ki, Duşeklər də həyatlarını musiqiyə həsr edib: Jozefina Dušek müğənni, Ksaver Dušek isə bəstəkar və pianoçu olub. Muzeydə mütəmadi olaraq kamera orkestrinin konsertləri və yaradıcılıq gecələri keçirilir [1; 115].

The museum tells not only about Mozart, but also about the Dušek family, the owners of the villa, and the development of Czech music in general. The point is that the Dušek family also dedicated their lives to music: Josefina Dušek was a singer, while Ksavere Dušek was a composer and pianist. Chamber orchestra concerts and creative evenings are regularly held in the museum [1; 115].

Among these, the *Niyazi House Museum*, dedicated to the People's Artist of the USSR, the prominent conductor and composer Niyazi, is the branch of the Azerbaijan State Museum of Musical Culture with the largest exhibition area and the most exhibits. It was opened in September 1994, 18 with the participation of national leader Heydar Aliyev. The apartment-museum consists of 5 rooms. The three memorial rooms are the dining room, bedroom and study, preserved as they were during the Maestro time. The other 2 rooms are used for exposition and artistic living rooms. The exposition displays photographs, posters, manuscripts of notes, programs and other exhibits reflecting Niyazis life and work from his childhood to the last years of his life. In the living room, photographs depicting Niyazis social activities, paintings donated to the Maestro in different years and acquired by the museum are displayed.

Throughout his life, Maestro Niyazi was the first and inimitable interpreter of new works in Azerbaijani music, and rendered exceptional services in promoting these works widely and gaining international fame. Starting from the 1950s, Niyazi's reputation spread not only to major cultural centers of the USSR but also to cities in Türkiye, Bulgaria, the Czech Republic, France, the United Kingdom, Germany, India, and other countries. «*Niyazi always showed the highest level in various directions of conducting – opera conductor, symphonic conductor, as well as accompaniment conductor. The Maestro, like a real symphony conductor, managed to subdue the orchestra to himself very quickly. The most prestigious orchestras took great pleasure in working with him. Niyazi performed with the most virtuosic soloists of his time-such as S. Richter, E. Gilels, M. Rostropovich, V. Cliburn, L. Oborin, L. Kogan, I. Oistrakh, R. Kerer, Y. Flier, L. Isakadze, V. Merzhanov, Y. Malinin, S. Knushevitsky, and many others – masterfully showcasing his skills as an accompanying conductor. It is no secret that, although Niyazi initially gave the impression of a stern and uncompromising person, he was extremely attentive and supportive towards young talents*» [4; 13].

The house museum of the prominent composer and pianist *Vagif Mustafazadeh*, who is the founder of jazz mugham, was established on July 28, 1989, by his mother, Ziver Aliyeva. In 1994, it gained the status of

a branch of the State Museum of Musical Culture of Azerbaijan Azerbaijan. 1214 museum objects are preserved in the museum. Among these items are photographs, records, paintings, posters, various documents, personal belongings, and other materials related to Vagif Mustafazadeh.

The museum, which has been operating since the overhaul in 2005, consists of 3 rooms. The exhibition presents photographs, documents, personal belongings, awards, musical instruments, etc. related to the life and work of the outstanding artist. Among the artist's personal belongings in the museum, an old radio always draws visitors' attention. Vagif Mustafazadeh eagerly listened to jazz music on this radio receiver from the age of 16 [5].

The house museum of Gara Garayev, the illustrious Azerbaijani composer and one of the notable figures of the 20th century, was inaugurated on October 1, 2018, to celebrate his 100th anniversary. The museum was created in the apartment where Gara Garayev lived with his family from 1918 to 1946. Here, the composer spent his youth and student years, writing his first works, including the ballet «Seven Beauties».

The house museum of Uzeyir Hajibeyli, the founder of Azerbaijani professional music, the author of the first opera in the East, the creator of the first folk musical instrument orchestra, the first state choir, and the first string quartet, as well as one of the co-founders and the first genuine members of the Academy of Sciences of the Azerbaijan SSR, a People's Artist of the USSR, and a two-time laureate of the second-class «Stalin» Prize, was established in the house where the composer lived from 1915 to 1942. The grand opening of the museum took place in 1975 with the participation of national leader Heydar Aliyev, November 20.

The Memorial Museum of Bulbul, the founder of Azerbaijani professional vocal art, a People's Artist of the USSR, a Stalin Prize laureate, a prominent public figure, and a professor, was established in 1976 through the personal initiative of the great leader Heydar Aliyev, the museum's grand opening ceremony took place on June 10, 1982.

The house museum of Leopold and Mstislav Rostropovich was established in 1998 in the house where Leopold Rostropovich, who laid the foundation for national cello art in Azerbaijan and created the first string quartet, lived with his family from 1925 to 1931, and where the world-renowned cellist Mstislav Rostropovich was born and spent his childhood. On March 4, 2002, the opening ceremony of the museum took place with the participation of a prominent performer.

Mstislav Rostropovich, who visited the home museum in Baku several times with his wife Galina Vishnevskaya, donated a wealth of archival materials to the museum. Among the materials are «*Mstislav Rostropovich's items, such as concert and conductor tails, a conductor's baton, as well as letters written to him in 1942 by his father and the famous Russian composer Alexander Glazunov, the programs of Leopold Rostropovich's performances, various diplomas and awards received by Mstislav Rostropovich at international competitions, and the book «Noble Calendar», which details the Rostropovich family's coat of arms and history. Sheyla Heydarova said that in the current year the exposition of the museum was enriched with more than three hundred new exhibits purchased from Moscow and St.Petersburg. In the two years of the museum's operation, fifteen hundred exhibits were collected*» [6; s. 27].

Up to 6,100 museum objects are protected in the main fund of the museum. This mainly includes manuscripts, scores, photographs, various documents, works related to different art forms, personal belongings, electronic media, and other materials.

The exposition of the museum consists of 4 rooms and hallways. The exhibition showcases materials that reflect the atmosphere of the home where the Rostropovich family lived, the environment of that time, Mstislav Rostropovich's childhood and youth, various stages of his life and creativity, as well as his connections to Baku. Among the unique exhibits, one can find a letter written by Leopold Rostropovich to his son (in 1942), carpets and furniture dating back to the early 20th century, autographs, concert attire, a conductor's baton, awards, and other materials [7; s. 10].

The building of the Bulbul House Museum located in Shusha dates back to the late 18th century. Bulbul spent his childhood years in this house where he was born. By the directive of the great leader Heydar Aliyev, the Bulbul House Museum was established in 1982 in a house consisting of two rooms and a balcony. Within a year, repairs were carried out in the building, work was carried out on the collection of museum items and the establishment of the exposition. The museum has hundreds of materials related to Bulbul's creative, educational, scientific-research and social activities. As a branch of the museum in Baku, the house museum in Shusha operated until 1992.

The museum's fund and exposition contains photographs, personal items, including the singers tambourine, concert posters from 1925-1926, manuscripts, articles and reports of the classic, various

documents, letters and other unique exhibits. Unfortunately, during the occupation, the museum was destroyed, and the materials preserved in it disappeared.

In August 2021, the reopening of Bulbul's House Museum in Shusha took place with the participation of President Ilham Aliyev and First Lady Mehriban Aliyeva.

Each item exhibited in the museum was brought from Bulbul's Memorial Museum in Baku. The staff of this museum, led by the author of the research work, directly participated in the establishment of the exhibition, the arrangement of the exhibits, the selection of appropriate spaces for display, and the resolution of other related issues [8; s. 4].

Currently, a newly created bust of Bulbul has been erected in the courtyard of the house museum. During the occupation of the city of Shusha, the vandalized bust of Bulbul was also detained in order to demonstrate Armenian brutality.

The courtyard of the house has been restored while preserving its original appearance. An open-air concert hall with a capacity of 250-300 people has been established in the museum's yard. Here, the first event took place within the framework of the VIII International Vocal Competition named after Bulbul, held on the occasion of the 125 th anniversary of Bulbul.

In the house museum in Shusha, modern technologies were used in accordance with the requirements of the time. On the monitor, recordings of Bulbul's life and creativity, from his childhood to the end of his life, as well as quotes and other materials about him are presented in Azerbaijani and Russian.

On one year, the museum has been visited by 40,000 guests.

Since there is no house museum for the great composer, conductor, public figure, folklorist, pedagogue, one of the founders of Azerbaijani classical music, the author of the first opera in European style in Azerbaijani music, and Honored Art Worker of the Azerbaijan SSR, Muslim Magomayev, his personal archive is kept in the archives of the Mammad Fuzuli Institute of Manuscripts of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences. The musical scores, reviews, correspondence, memoirs, folklore samples collected in Lankaran, songs composed to the lyrics of M. S. Ordubadi, and critical thoughts in his archive – all of these materials are an important source for studying the history of Azerbaijani composition in the 20 th century, the performance school, acting, and the theater school [10; s. 6].

Taking into account the trend of recent decades, we can note that museums can be called places of storage of not only material, but also intangible cultural heritage. In particular, we can attribute this to museums of literature, theater and music profile, because along with the material witnesses of the listed museums, their role in the development of society is investigated, promoted and demonstrated.

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UDC 539.175.1**HOUSE AND MEMORIAL MUSEUMS OF OUTSTANDING REPRESENTATIVES OF MUSICAL ART**

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Taking into account the trend of recent decades, we can note that museums can be called places of storage of not only tangible, but also intangible cultural heritage. In particular, we can attribute this to museums of literature, theater and music profile, because along with the material witnesses of the listed museums, their role in the development of society is investigated, promoted and demonstrated. We find it appropriate to introduce some of the music museums dedicated to the lives and works of numerous prominent figures in the field of music. Of course, it is not possible to discuss thousands of such museums, but it is necessary to provide information about a few interesting museums related to each group. The museums under study are institutions that carry out the collection, preservation, study and display of materials on the development of musical culture. The first proto-museums with a music focus began to emerge in Europe in the late 16 th century, based on collections from musicians and theaters, as well as musical monuments preserved in churches and monasteries. These collections included manuscript scores of musical works, opera parts and play texts, and rare musical instruments (such as violin, viola, viol, cello, double bass, etc.) created by prominent artisans. Collections of musical instruments created by Italian artisans from the 16 th to 18 th centuries, such as Gasparo da Salò, Amati, Guarneri, Antonio Stradivari, Montagnana, Bergonzi, and Ruggieri, held the greatest material and artistic value. Historically, two major groups of music museums have formed worldwide. The first group includes museums focused on displaying items from various eras, cultures, and artistic schools. For example, the Museum of the History of European Instruments in Trondheim, the A. Stradivari Museum in Cremona, and others. The second group comprises the heritage of the world's prominent musical figures. Museums dedicated to V.A. Mozart in Salzburg, J.S. Bach in Eisenach, L. Beethoven in Bonn, N.A. Rimsky-Korsakov in Saint Petersburg, F.I. Chaliapin in Kislovodsk, Solomiya Krushelnyska in Lviv, and others. Museums worldwide and in Azerbaijan, including music museums, stand out for their unique collections and archives. It is our duty to preserve these values and pass them on to future generations.

Key words: Music, museum, memorial, opera, conductor, exposition, fund, collection.

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UDC 962.48**ЗАСОБИ ВИКОРИСТАННЯ ЗРАЗКІВ ВІТЧИЗНЯНОГО ТА СВІТОВОГО МИСТЕЦТВА
У НАВЧАЛЬНОМУ ПРОЦЕСІ ПОЧАТКОВИХ КЛАСІВ**

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Показані способи використання зразків національного і світового мистецтва в навчальному процесі молодших класів і розповідається про важливість цього у формуванні світогляду учнів, розвитку естетичних почуттів і прищеплення моральних якостей. Автор спеціально представила результати своєї дослідницької роботи.

Таким чином, етичні та естетичні норми, сформовані в азербайджанському суспільстві і володіють високими моральними цінностями, можуть бути інтегровані в загальнолюдські ідеї завдяки своєму гуманістичному характеру. Як показує практика, національно-духовні цінності, культурна спадщина та історичні реалії, що передаються азербайджанським народом із покоління в покоління, з цікавістю сприймаються народами світу. У той же час світова культура і загальнолюдські цінності також стають чинником розвитку духовного життя нашого народу.

Ключові слова: навчання, навчальний процес, початкові класи, мистецтво, загальнолюдська та національна культура.